

PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENTS AND PROCESS SIMULATION OF LARGE SANDWICH STRUCTURES FOR INDUSTRIAL WIND TURBINE BLADES

Allan Roulund Gersborg¹, Jacob Eneberg Jørgensen², René Gaarde², Harry Alkemade³

Santhosh Kumar Vanaparthi⁴ and Shashidhar Patil⁴

LM Wind Power,

¹SCION DTU, Diplomvej 373N, DK-2800 Lyngby, Denmark

²Rollesmøllevvej 1, DK-6400 Lunderskov, Denmark

³J. Duikerweg 15A, Heerhugowaard, 1703 DH, Netherlands

⁴RMZ Infinity, Tower-B, III Floor, Bangalore, 560 016, India

Email: alrg@lmwindpower.com, web page: <http://www.lmwindpower.com/>

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ABSTRACT

This work addresses material characterization and simulation of sandwich parts for industrial wind turbine blades produced with the VARTM process. In-plane permeability measurements have been performed both on the pure constituents of the sandwich and on the actual sandwich layup. It is found that Darcy's law is not expected to give a good quantitative agreement for long simulation times which limits the value of commercially available software.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Company profile

Danish based LM Wind Power is the world's largest independent supplier of wind turbine blades, operating 13 manufacturing facilities in China, India, Poland, Spain, Denmark, US, Canada and Brazil. With 5-7 new blade developments a year and a long list of records and patents, innovation is one of the key attributes of LM Wind Power which has technology hubs in Denmark, The Netherlands and India. LM Wind Power designs and builds blades that are optimized to the remaining parts of the turbine with the aim of finding the optimum balance between performance, reliability and cost. All designs are validated and tested beyond requirements in the company's in-house wind tunnel and full scale testing facilities. The current product portfolio includes blades up to 73.5 meters length.

Key figures

- Revenue 2014 EURm 588
- Roughly 22 wind turbine blades produced per day
- A typical blade is longer than 50m and made of glass fabrics and infused with polyester resin
- Glass consumption in LM 100 ton/day

LM Wind Power specializes in the full range of disciplines within rotor blade development and composites technology from aerodynamics, blade construction, materials and manufacturing processes to full-scale testing. The company employs more than 300 engineers and is continuously expanding and looking for more skilled engineers to meet the increased demand for innovative rotor solutions that boost energy performance and reduce cost of energy. During the past 35 years, LM Wind Power has produced more than 175,000 blades since 1978 and almost one in four wind turbines installed worldwide have LM Wind Power blades.

1.2 Motivation for contribution to ICCM community

A wind turbine blade consists of several different components and this contribution focus on the sandwich part of a shear web as shown in Figure 1. A shear web is elegantly tapered in the longitudinal direction of the blade, whereas it reduces to a simple sandwich panel in transverse direction due to the flat web body.

The materials used for the sandwich panel are: Glass fabric as skin plies together with either balsa wood or foam as core material. Today balsa wood is grown commercially in two geographic locations in the world being Papua New Guinea and Ecuador. Moreover, balsa wood is sensitive to moisture and fungi which also motivates the use of industrial foams, such as the foam shown in Figure 2. In order to ensure a good wet out of the laminate a surface finish with holes and grooves is integrated in the foam.

This contribution studies characterization of the flow properties of industrial foam with the VARTM process in terms of the permeability, see reference [3] and the references therein for an introduction to the VARTM process and permeability. The aim is to provide a basis for process simulation of blade components in order to lower prototype costs and shorten prototype time. Process simulation is typically based on Darcy's law [4, 5], below it is shown in its simplest integrated form for 1D flow in a rectangular frame of reference

$$t = \frac{\mu\varphi}{2K\Delta p} x^2 \quad (1)$$

where t is time, μ is the dynamic viscosity, φ is the porosity, K the permeability, Δp is the pressure difference driving the flow and x is the flow front position, see [3] and the references therein for a detailed introduction. Equation (1) is used as a reference model in the evaluation of the observed experimental response.

The size of a shear web has the consequence that the material is not delivered in one piece. For that reason the effect of misaligned grooves on the flow capacity in the 1-direction of the foam is investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

2.1 Permeability test with foam

The experimental setup is shown in Figure 3 and snapshots of the flow fronts are seen in Figure 4. A vacuum gauge pressure of just -0.3bar is used in order to slow down the flow front progression in order to capture it with available equipment. Although a non-uniform flow front is observed, a fit to a porous flow model is attempted since that is what commercially available software is based on.

The flow front position is plotted as a function of time, see Figure 5. It is found that a power law model with an exponent of 1.3 to 1.4 fits well with the data, that is, Darcy's law will for long simulation times not predict the response accurately since it uses an exponent of 2.0.

Finally, it is noted that bubble formation throughout the foam panel was observed when the foam was approaching 100% filling, see Figure 6. This observation is relevant since it shows that it is important also to explain for air flow during the complete process because important defects can evolve rapidly. Air entrapped in the infusion medium at the inlet is judged as the cause for the bubbles. However, the regular pattern suggests that it somehow is related to the holes and possibly also the low vacuum level (vacuum gauge pressure of -0.3bar).

Figure 1 This paper focus on the (shear) webs in a wind turbine blade, see subfigure (a) and (b). The webs are sandwich panels consisting of core material covered with skin plies as seen in subfigure (c). The web is the simplest sandwich component in a blade because of a simple geometry due to the flat web body.

Figure 2 Industrial foam with surface finish. Holes $\text{\O}2\text{mm}$ in rectangular $20\text{mm} \times 40\text{mm}$ pattern. Grooves $2\text{mm} \times 2\text{mm}$. Thickness 25mm .

Figure 3 Setup for K11 permeability of foam. VARTM infusion of foam on a glass table with tracking of flow front at a vacuum gauge pressure of -0.3bar in order to slow down the experiment.

Figure 4 Snapshots of K11 permeability with foam. The bottom flow front towards the glass plate is faster than the top flow front.

Figure 5 Results from K11 permeability with foam. The bottom flow front towards the glass plate is faster than the top flow front.

Figure 6 Formation of small bubbles when the flow front reaches the end and the foam fills up. This observation is relevant since it shows that it is important also to explain for air flow during the complete process because important defects can evolve rapidly. The bubbles are visible when the pictures are viewed as a movie, or as small dots if two pictures are subtracted. Air entrapped in the infusion medium at the inlet is judged as the cause for the bubbles. However, the regular pattern suggests that it somehow is related to the holes and possibly also the low vacuum level (vacuum gauge pressure of -0.3bar).

2.2 Permeability test with sandwich layup

The experimental setup is shown for a K11 test in Figure 7 and for a K22 test in Figure 8. The permeability experiments are done with the actual sandwich layup using the VARTM process with a vacuum gauge pressure of -0.85bar.

Due to the relatively large grooves in foam the K11 test it is difficult to define the flow front. The reason is that the permeability contrast between the foam and the glass is large, which could motivate independent modelling of the materials. From a practical point of view the experiment is very fast.

For the K22 test the flow front is well defined since it is aligned by the foam grooves. When plotting the data from the K22 experiment, it is found that a power law model with an exponent of 2.4 fits well, see Figure 9. That is, for long simulation times Darcy's law will overestimate the flow front progression since it uses an exponent of 2.0.

2.3 Discussion of permeability tests

Based on the conducted experiments it is concluded that Darcy's law is not expected to give a good quantitative prediction of the flow front position for large simulation times. Moreover, there is an open modelling challenge for flow in the longitudinal direction since the flow front is not well defined as seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7 K11 permeability experiment. Layup: Biaxial plies - foam - biaxial plies. The flow front is not well defined.

Figure 8 K22 permeability experiment using the VARTM process. Layup: Biaxial plies - foam - biaxial plies. The flow front is well defined.

Figure 9 Power law correlation for the experiment seen in Figure 8. It is found that a power law with an exponent 2.4 fits well with the data.

2.4 Flow capacity test of assembly of foam panels

The experimental setup is shown in Figure 10 which measures the flow capacity of the foam for various degree of groove misalignment, see Figure 11.

Surprisingly, the degree of misalignment does not cause a significant difference in the filling time for the foam which is of the order of 4 minutes for all three experiments. This is explained by the filling and absorption of resin in the foam is a slower process such that the misalignment does not influence the filling time.

As shown in Figure 12, a difference in the flow capacity of the order of 15% is observed between the aligned and misaligned grooves. Although only three tests have been carried out, the results suggest that a single groove is limiting the flow capacity since the number of grooves appears not to be significant.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The experimental permeability and flow capacity results show some of the complexity of VARTM infusion of the simplest sandwich structure in a wind turbine blade. It is found that Darcy's law is not expected to give a good quantitative agreement for long simulation times which limits the value of commercially available software. This finding motivates improved theoretical models for the VARTM process and software updates.

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- [4] RTM-Worx software made by Polyworx B.V., Alexander Bellstraat 2, 7442 DE Nijverdal, The Netherlands.
- [5] PAM-RTM software made by ESI Group.

Figure 10 Setup for flow capacity experiment with groove misalignment. VARTM infusion of foam on a glass table with measurement of injected mass and tracking of flow front at a vacuum gauge pressure of -0.85bar . Staples are used to fix foam sheets.

Figure 11 Flow patterns for various degree of misalignment. It was unintended that the experiment with 9 misalignments is 11% longer than the other. It is not disqualified, since it has little influence on the results and since it was not possible to redo the experiment.

Figure 12 Results for groove misalignment experiment. It is found that the flow capacity [kg/s] drops of the order of 15% if grooves are misaligned. In this experiment the number of misalignments has an insignificant effect on the reduction in flow capacity. Moreover, the filling time of the foam is of the order of 4minutes independent of the number of misalignments. The injected mass after 1 minute is considered due to initial data recording problems for the experiment with 2 misalignments.